
The Role of Motivation in Teaching and Learning English Language in Secondary Classes

Jahirul Islam, Language Instructor, English Language Institute, Jazan University, Saudi Arabia

Dr. Muktar Babiker Ali Juma, Lecturer, English Language Institute, Jazan University, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

This study aims to detect the role of Motivation in the classroom, which is influential in ensuring learning and teaching the English language. This study helps the teachers to do their responsibilities with Motivation and to make their job successful. This research examined learners' Motivation in the classroom, teachers' role, and student feedback for promoting Motivation. To accomplish this study, feedback has been taken from one hundred students and many teachers. The learners have gone through some questionnaires. Teachers have been interviewed, and surveys have also been taken among the learners. Throughout the passage of the research, some major themes have been unveiled. The first theme was classroom atmosphere at the secondary level. The second central theme was the curriculum. The third theme was about connecting learning materials to the student's lives. The fourth central theme was detecting the factors responsible for learners' Motivation. The fifth central theme was the use of some techniques in the classroom to provide opportunities for the students to be involved in the teaching-learning process. Motivation has traditionally been considered an independent variable in studying academic Motivation in a language-learning setting. Many distinct motivational types have been observed: Motivation about the language, Motivation in classroom situations, Motivation about interaction with confidence, external Motivation, whether the learners need to be required, and self-reported Motivation. Motivation about the language is found to be of particular importance in predicting outcomes. Improving students' motivation levels would have many implications for language learning. Throughout my investigation, it has been found that there are many issues in motivating

learners to learn English as a second or a foreign language. In my study, it has also been concentrated that teaching strategies substantially impact the students' Motivation in the classroom and their day-to-day lives. The major themes mentioned above can be applied in almost any situation, grade level, or subject area. Applying these strategies can be handy for teachers to motivate students to learn the English language.

Keywords: Motivation, English Language, strategies, major themes, passage of research.

Introduction

Motivation is one of the essential factors which plays a significant role in the teaching-learning process. It is considered an integral part of the achievement of any goal. It is a critical factor that positively influences educational learning, especially in learning English as a second language. Woolfolk (1998) defines "Motivation as an internal state that arouses, directs and maintains behavior." Salvin (2001) defines "Motivation as an internal process that activates, guides and maintains behavior over time." In light of these definitions, Motivation can be considered a process that contributes to the success of L2 teaching and learning at the secondary level.

It is noticed that how students become successful or fail in learning the English language due to Motivation. If Motivation does not stand properly, the learners suffer, leading to failure.

Properly motivated students can appropriately achieve the language. Dornyei (2002) stated that the learner's enthusiasm, commitment, and persistence are the key determinants of success or failure. This research investigates the role of Motivation of the students of classes VIII, IX, and X in the secondary institution Regal World School, Moradabad, UP, India. By nature of Motivation, the researcher is trying to determine the types of motivation students have and the roles of Motivation that influence their teaching-learning process. The curriculum at the secondary level puts importance on teaching and learning English communicatively. However, unfortunately, the students do not become competent in using English in the classroom environment after finishing their secondary education. The students need more Motivation to learn English for communication purposes. This research aims to discover the sources of Motivation, factors of Motivation, obstacles in Motivation, causes of demotivation, and measures to be taken to motivate the learners and create a positive and robust environment for learning the English language at the secondary level.

Background of Research Study:

Being an English teacher, the author finds the factor of Motivation has a vital contribution to the English teaching-learning process. The author observes that to study secondary level students to discover shortcomings in English teaching and learning. The study takes place in such a location where the author finds students from different family backgrounds and different geographical locations. Some are from rural, and some are from urban areas. The author feels to study factors of Motivation of the students of the school 'Regal World School' situated in Uttar Pradesh, India, which plays a significant role in learning English. The author emphasizes studying this particular school because it can depict an ideal picture of the English teaching-learning process in India and especially to motivate the teachers and students in the domain of the English language.

Objectives

There are many objectives of my research article. They are mentioned below:

- It enables the learners to understand the importance of the English language in their day-to-day life.
- It enables the teachers to understand the challenges faced by the students in learning the English language.
- It enables the teachers to understand the factors responsible for learners' Motivation.
- It enhances the teachers to find out the challenges faced by the students in learning the English language.
- It helps the students to utilize their potential in learning English.
- It enhances the teacher's understanding of the factors related to students' failures in obtaining the target language.
- It enlightens teachers and students to sort out a shared vision to attain knowledge of the English language.
- It enhances the teachers to dominate the teaching-learning process with high spirits.
- It helps to execute different teaching strategies and methods in teaching-learning.
- It enables the learners to involve themselves with a clear vision for learning English.
- It enables the learners to realize the importance of learning English as an excellent language for communication worldwide.
- It enables learners to achieve knowledge of the English language perfectly.

Literature Review:

In this section of the research study, the author refers to some of the reviews of experts on Motivation in the teaching-learning process. A study that has conducted by Lamb (2004) argued in his study that the respondents responded that the majority of them are motivated toward English language learning because of the following factors: they thought that English would help their careers in the future, it is a pleasure to study, can help me meet foreigners & learn about foreign countries, my parents encourage me to learn it, and It is an essential school subject.

Gao (2004) explained in his doctoral dissertation on the Motivation of Chinese learners of English is

an example of a study engaging a more comprehensive structure and recognized the following five motivational magnitudes of Chinese learners of English: integrativeness, appraisal of English class, linguistic self-confidence, instrumentality, and direct contact with a foreigner.

Recently, Liu (2007) conducted a study on the Motivation of university students in China to learn English. The result shows that most of the respondents agree that they can learn about foreign cultures and countries and that English will help them to connect the foreign people and English help them to travel on every side of the world.

A study that has been conducted by Gardner (2001) claimed that most learners are motivated toward English language learning by the following integrative motivational factors:

- People learn English to know more about the world.
- People learn English to communicate with others.
- English helps me in my travel overseas.
- Another study has shown that students are motivated to learn English because they are trying to communicate with non-native speakers of English in an international environment.

According to Oxford English Dictionary Online, Motivation is "the conscious or unconscious stimulus for action towards a desired goal, especially resulting from psychological or social factors; the factors giving purposes or directions to human or animal behavior. Now also more generally: it means the reason a person has for acting in a particular way, a motive." Concerning Baumeister and Vohs (2007), Ozen (2017) defines *Motivation* as "a state where the individual displays various attitudes voluntarily in order to achieve a specific goal (p.35).

Choosri and Intharaksa (2011) believe that Motivation is both internal and external and can also be noteworthy because it helps one to learn the identity oneself and advocate that Motivation directly affects the achievement of learners. Choosri and Intharaksa (2011) stress that

Motivation is the critical factor that may explain why learners disregard or achieve learning English. Gardner and Lambert (1972) (Quoted in Choosri & Intharaksa 2011) proclaim that combining all those efforts and desires supports achieving learning goals. This prompts the learners to make conscious efforts for their goals and keep them sustained for a long time.

Recently, some researchers have explored and discussed other dimensions and classifications of Motivation in the context of learning second/foreign languages (Moskovsky & Alrabai, 2009). Intrinsic and extrinsic Motivation is, for example, essential themes in the recent debate on Motivation. Intrinsic Motivation is defined by Woolfolk (2016) as "motivation that stems from factors such as interest or curiosity" (p.374), while "extrinsic motivation involves doing something to obtain something else (a means to an end)" (Santrock, 2004, p.418)

In Dubai, Qashoa (2006) observed students' integrative and instrumental Motivation for learning English in UAE state secondary schools, and the findings exhibited that the students have a higher gradation of instrumental Motivation than integrative one. These students showed that they learn English because they want a better job since the labor market offers higher-paying jobs for English experts.

Dörnyei (1998), as cited in Gilakjani, Leong, and Sabouri (2012), points out: "In taxonomy, Motivation consists of three levels: the language level, the learner level, and the learning situation level. The motivation processes at the language level can be defined broadly by consuming the traditional concepts of integrative and instrumental Motivation; at the learner level, Motivation includes the impact of various individual characteristics of language learners, such as the need for achievement and self-confidence. "The learning situation level is also influenced by several intrinsic and extrinsic motives" (p. 10). From the teacher's perspective, Gilakjani, Leong, and Sabouri (2012) have identified three levels of students' Motivation: finding the learner's passion, changing learners' reality, and connecting to learning activities.

Definitions and Major Types of Motivation:

Motivation plays a significant role in any activity. It is nothing but a prerequisite factor to do something in this world. It is a spirit to convert a situation into action. It has a significant role in learning the English language. It also plays a dominant role in teaching the English language also. The success or failure depends on the degree of Motivation. The outcome will also be good if the degree of Motivation is good. We can obtain a prosperous outcome if the degree of Motivation is higher. Motivation accelerates our actions to achieve the target. At present, the word motivation has been a part of effective language learning. Many researchers have opined to define this term. It means the reason for the action, the desire to complete a task. Snowman, McCown, and Biehler (2009) defined *Motivation* as an individual's willingness "to expend a certain amount of effort to achieve a particular goal under a particular set of circumstances" (p. 406). Gardner (1985) opines that in foreign language learning, Motivation is "the combination of effort plus a desire to achieve the goal of learning the language" (p. 10). To him, the Motivation to learn a foreign language has three elements: aspiration, endeavor, and result. That means a motivated L2 learner will aim to learn the target language and achieve something due to his effort. In classroom teaching, Motivation indicates "the degree to which students invest attention and effort in various pursuits....motivation is rooted in students' subjective experiences, especially those connected to their willingness to engage in learning activities and their reasons for doing so" (Brophy, 2010, p. 3).

Motivation offers a source of energy responsible for why learners decide to make an effort, how long they are willing to sustain an activity, how hard they will pursue it, and how connected they feel to the activity (Rost, 2001, p. 1). *Motivation* is an individual attribute describing the psychological qualities underlying behavior about a particular task (MacIntyre, MacMaster & Baker, 2001).

Spolsky (1989) has divided Motivation into five comprehensive parts: 1) Enhancing language-related values and attitudes of learners, 2) Increasing the learners' expectancy of success. 3) Building students more goal-oriented. 4) Making

the teaching materials relevant for the learners. 5) Making realistic learner beliefs.

Motivation is considered an integral part of the achievement of any goal. It is an essential factor that positively influences any educational learning process, especially in learning a second language. Woolfolk (1998) defines "Motivation as an internal state that arouses, directs and maintains behavior" (P.372). Salvin (2001) defines "Motivation as an internal process that activates, guides and maintains behavior over time." (P.345)

Types of Motivation:

Robert Gardner (1982) was influenced mainly by Mower's idea of Motivation. Gardner presented Mower's idea as the basis for his research. Gardner's model tends to reflect four basic structures of L2 learning. These structures are:

- Social and cultural environment
- Learner's differences.
- The setting in which learning takes place.
- Linguistics outcomes.

In the light of this model, Motivation works on three levels.

- Efforts: refer to the drive of the learner.
- Desire: refers to the want of the learner.
- Affect: refers to the learner's emotional reaction.

Based on these fundamentals, the learner can be categorized into two stages of Motivation: i. instrumental motivation and ii. Integrative Motivation.

Instrumental Motivation. Instrumental Motivation refers to a practical or pragmatic reason for language study. Instrumental motivations for language learning include

- passing a language requirement,
- getting a monetary reward such as an increase in pay grade for language competence, or
- having a better chance of getting into medical school.

Gardner (1983) describes instrumental Motivation as "Learning a language because of someone or less clearly perceived utility it might have for the learner." (p. 2003). More specifically, a learner is instrumentally motivated when he or she wants to learn a language "to pass an exam, to use it when visiting a foreign country and to get a well-paid job." (Wilkins, 1972, p. 184). Gardner and Lambert (1992) considered instrumental Motivation as a means to get social and economic rewards through second language learning. On the other hand, Chalak and Kassaian (2010) state that integrative motivation is "The desire to learn a second language/foreign language to communicate with the people of the second language society and mix up in their culture." Integrative Motivation is "an openness to identify at least in part with another language community." (Gardner & Masgoret, 2003, P. 126). Ellis (1997) pointed out that Motivation varies from person to person depending on the learning context and task. (p. 76). So the purpose of this paper is to investigate the motivation type more common among Indian students in the secondary section of learning English as a foreign language.

Brown (2000) suggested that learners prefer combining these two types for learning a target language. Wong. Fillmore (1991) viewed three conditions necessary for learning L2. A) The need for motivated students to learn the target language. B) Native speakers' support to learn L2. C) Contact between native speakers of the target language and learners.

1. *Integrative Motivation.*

Integrative motivated learners want to learn the target language to understand better and get to know the people who speak it and mix it up in their culture. Integrative Motivation is "an openness to recognize at least in part with another language community "Gardner and Margaret, (2003, P.126). Ellis (1997) explains that learners acquire a target language to accomplish the yearning to mix up with the people and culture of the target language.

The effort of James Gardner and associates characterizes this conceptualization of Motivation. As well-defined by Gardner (2001), integrativeness

is one of two significant factors that influence overall Motivation. It is a complex hypothesis reflecting curiosity in learning a foreign language to become nearer to the L2 community. Thus, the term symbolizes attitudes toward learning foreign languages and towards the L2 group generally and the learner's inclination to relate with members of that L2 community (Dörnyei, 2005). Attitudes toward the learning situation constitute the second component of Gardner's two-pronged theory of Motivation. Gardner (2001) explains that, in a classroom context, this term includes attitudes towards the teacher, classmates, coursework, activities associated with the course, and all other aspects of the state where the language is learned. Integrativeness and attitudes towards the learning situation contribute to overall Motivation to learn the language. In this conceptualization of the term, a motivated individual makes an effort to learn the language (i.e., does homework, contributes in class, etc.), wants to learn the language, and will enjoy learning the language (Gardner, 2001).

2. *Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation:*

On the contrary, some researchers, such as Au (1988), suggested that both types are challenging to distinguish into different categories. One important aspect we should remember regarding this dichotomy of Motivation is that it can be seen in the words of Ellis (1997:76) "as complementary rather than as distinct and oppositional." Ellis (1997:76) pointed out that Motivation varies from person to person depending on the learning context and task. Through previous studies, it has been revealed that the dichotomy of integrative and instrumental Motivation has been the focus of many researchers. Baily and Garratt (2002, p.49) have classified Motivation as Intrinsic and Extrinsic. Woolfolk (1998) defines intrinsic Motivation as "Motivation that stems from factors such as interest or curiosity "(P.374)

According to Santrock (2004), "Extrinsic motivation involves doing something to obtain something else (a means to an end)" (P.418)

Many researchers looked at integrative and instrumental Motivation as intrinsic and extrinsic Motivation. As discussed earlier, the types of Motivation vary from context to context. As viewed by Ellis (1997), now the question arises of

which type would be more effective in our Indian context. So the purpose of this study is to investigate the type of Motivation that is more popular among Indian students in learning English as a Second Language. Furthermore, the study will offer an adequate vision in understanding the students' priorities and discuss some innovations and improvements regarding ELT and L2 learning.

Research Design

My present research study tries to identify why students are motivated towards English language learning at Secondary schools in India. The study also depicts the teachers using some motivational skills to pursue the goals of teaching English in secondary classes. To sum up my research, I have used the following research methods and techniques. These are mentioned below:

- The study is descriptive, in which a quantitative questionnaire has been used to collect data. The descriptive quantitative approach examines the phenomenon by collecting the data numerically.
- Moreover, "Survey research designs are procedures in quantitative research in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or to the entire population to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of the population."
- I have used qualitative and quantitative methods while collecting and analyzing data. Qualitative research produces in-depth answers to the research question, while quantitative research generates numerical data or data that can be converted into numbers for a statistical assessment.
- The research procedure has been completed by collecting books, journals, and articles from the library. Journal and scholarly articles have been collected from educational and academic databases.

Tools of data collection:

I have used different tools to collect data. These are stated below:

- I have prepared some Questionnaires for the students of different secondary classes related to the learning of the English language as a second language.

- I have used some questionnaires for the teachers related to the teaching difficulties in teaching the English Language.
- I have prepared some particular questions for students to check their Motivation to learn the English Language.
- I have used some scales to differentiate the level of Motivation among different types of students.
- I have used standard questionnaires to understand the motivational difference between male and female learners.
- I have collected some data from group discussions.
- I have interviewed some English Language teachers for their views about teaching the English Language.
- I have collected some data from practical classroom teaching.

Questionnaire for the learners:

The following research questions were focused on in this study:

1. What significant factors de-motivate students to learn English at secondary schools?
2. Is there any difference in the Motivation of students from rural and urban areas?
3. Is there any difference in the Motivation of male and female students?
4. Is there any variance in the Motivation of students from government and private schools?
5. What is students' achievement in English subject?
6. Is there any significant impact of students' Motivation for learning English on their achievement?

7. What is the level of students' Motivation for learning English at secondary schools?
8. Do the learners have goals for English language learning?
9. Are the students motivated to study English as an essential means of communication in their professions?
10. Do the teachers play an essential role in motivating them to learn English?
11. Are the learners curious to learn English as global means of communication?
12. What are the main factors responsible for motivating students to learn the English language?

Data Collection Procedure:

The researcher sought approval from the head of the school before interviewing students and teachers. The learners have also been informed of the study, and they were guaranteed that their participation is benevolent and that their names would not be exposed in the publication of this study.

After having the consent of the participants, the questionnaires were distributed among students, and they were directed to fill in the questionnaire in the presence of the researcher. I have collected data from different classes. The researcher also

interviewed some English teachers for practical information related to the Motivation in teaching the English Language. All the participants responded to the questionnaire and passed it to the researcher.

Findings:

Table I

The following table I shows the demographic information of participants in the categories of gender, age, and geographical background of the participants. It has been observed that several male participants are more interested in learning English, and students from urban areas are more interested in learning the English language.

Table II

Table II shows students' level of interest in learning the English language. It was found that most of the students strongly agreed to learn English for material achievements and personality development. Only a few notes of the students do not have an interest in the English language.

Statements	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Neutral
English is useful for our future career.	10	15	70	5
English will help to interact with foreigners.	5	20	60	15
English helps me to travel abroad.	5	10	75	10
English helps me to do international business	2	30	60	8
English helps me to go for higher studies.	5	20	75	0
English enhances the outlook.	20	40	30	10

English helps me to learn about other cultures and history	10	70	10	10
I learn English to develop my personality	15	60	20	5
My family motivates to learn English	15	70	10	5
Digital media inspires me to learn English	5	70	20	5
Electronics media motivates me to learn English	10	60	20	10
My teachers inspire me to learn English	10	50	30	10
I feel English is necessary for my life	10	40	40	10
I learn English for the development of my personal life	10	70	10	10
English guides me to develop my culture	40	10	10	30

III. Findings from teachers in the field of Motivation:

The author also interviews some English teachers to know the factors related to Motivation. The teachers responded according to their practical observations according to the different levels of students. It is shown in the following table. This table shows that as the students promote to the next level, the intensity of Motivation grows to learn English.

Class	Age group	% of fully motivated students.	% of less / not motivated students.
VIII	12-13	25%	75%
IX	14-15	65%	35%
X	16-18	75%	25%

IV. The author conducted another study among 100 secondary section students about the sources of Motivation. The following chart shows the influence of parents, teachers, and digital media. It shows that teachers, parents, and social media are very significant in motivating students. Teachers play a greater role than parents and social media. The factor behind this is that most parents need to be made aware of the significance of the English language. In contrast, teachers are primarily aware of the importance of the English Language, and they can quickly motivate the learners. However, social media also influences students to learn the English language.

Table V: Integrative Motivation

As cited above, *integrative Motivation* in foreign or second language learning was defined as the desire to be a part of recognized or essential members of the community or the society that speaks the language. Table V shows the level of integrative Motivation of the students in this study.

<i>Contents to test level of motivation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>S.D</i>	<i>Level of Motivation.</i>
1. Learning English helps me integrate more easily into English speaking community.	6.07	0.208	High
2. Learning English makes me better understand and appreciate the ways of life of native English speakers.	5.21	0.456	High
3. Learning English enables me to discuss interesting topics with people from other socio-cultural backgrounds.	5.04	0.778	High
4. English language enables me to keep in touch with friends abroad.	4.45	0.502	High
5. English Language helps me participate freely in academic, social, and professional activities among other socio-cultural groups.	5.07	0.325	High
6. Learning English helps me convey my knowledge & information to other people.	4.38	0.493	High
7. English language helps me enjoy traveling to foreign countries.	5.16	0.400	High
8. English language enables me understand and appreciate arts & literature in English speaking cultures and traditions.	5.07	0.405	High
9. Learning English helps me to communicate easily with others online globally.	4.78	0.227	High

10. Learning English helps me become an open-minded and sociable person.	5.02	0.333	High
<i>Mean of measure</i>	5.025	0.412	High

From Table V, the integrative Motivation of the participants in the study is relatively high, with the mean for the full measure of 4.38. The mean for items in the measure ranges from 4.38 to 6.07. Item 1 shows the highest mean score, and item 6 shows the lowest mean score among the items.

Table: VI: Instrumental Motivation:

Instrumental Motivation contains the concepts of purely practical value in learning a foreign or second language to obtain learners' careers or business prospects, giving them more prestige and power, retrieving scientific and technical information, or just passing a course of their study in school. Table VI shows the students' instrumental Motivation level in this research study.

<i>Content of items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>S.D</i>	<i>Level of Motivation.</i>
1. English learning is important because I want it for my future career.	5.55	0.532	High
1. English is important because it will help me get a good job in international Companies.	5.64	0.542	High
2. English learning is important because it will help me get more opportunities to get a good career abroad.	5.35	0.521	High
3. Learning English is important because it enables me have a chance to go abroad for higher education.	5.57	0.522	High
4. I mainly focus on using English for class evaluations and examinations.	5.33	0.410	High
5. Learning English is important because I can get a lot of useful information for my work in the future.	5.45	0.425	High
6. I am interested in reading only English textbooks in my school.	4.78	0.478	High
7. I focus more on English language to earn university education in the future.	5.45	0.500	High
8. Learning English helps me become a knowledgeable and confident person.	5.11	0.498	High

9. Learning English helps me become an educated person	4.99	0.398	High
10. Being proficient in English makes me respectable person society.	5.25	0.412	High
11. Being proficient in English language enables me more success and achieve the best in my life.	5.10	0.408	High
Mean of measure	5.29	0.470	High

Note: S.D (Standard deviation.)

From Table V and Table VI, we can see a difference between the mean of integrative Motivation and instrumental Motivation. The mean score of instrumental Motivation is higher than that of integrative Motivation (5.29 compared to 5.025).

Discussion:

From this study, the author finds that the students are highly motivated to learn English as a foreign language. The findings answered the research questions about the level of the students' Motivation. Based on the comparison and assessment, the author finds that the students in the study are more instrumentally motivated to learn English than integrative Motivation. The learners' affinity towards instrumental Motivation could be explained by the students' focus on getting a good job that requires proficiency in the English language. Surrounded by the factors studied (gender, the school year, the time learning English, and the parental ability to speak English) that might influence the students' Motivation in English language learning, only the different school years and the parental ability to speak English have significant influences on the students' Motivation. Unambiguously, second-year students have more Motivation in English language learning than first-year students. Second-year students have spent more time in the school learning environment than first-year students. This has led to changes in attitudes towards English learning. This is the reason for explaining the difference in Motivation in English language learning. The pupils who have parents who can speak English also have a higher level of Motivation in English language learning. The importance of parents on attitudes, Motivation, and behaviors in learning, in general, is consistent

with many previous studies. Speaking and listening skills were the most troublesome for the study's students. These two language skills are critical to communicating with other people. Therefore, more attention should be given to building training programs, curriculums, teaching methodology, and study resources to improve these language skills. Based on the findings of this study, the consequences are unique for only specific students that participated in the study. The students have a high level of Motivation in both instrumental and integrative aspects, whereas instrumental Motivation is expressively higher than integrative Motivation.

Recommendations:

This study could address the following resolutions to solve the problems of learners' Motivation toward English language learning.

- Parents have the responsibility to support their children financially and spiritually.
- Both parents and teachers should explain the importance of the English language.
- The learners should be given clear objectives of the English language.
- Social organizations should conduct campaigns to make people cautious about the importance of the English language.
- Teachers should be trained to motivate the students.
- Educational organizations should have a team of motivational speakers to encourage learners to pursue the English language.

- The government should prepare motivational seminars for parents to encourage their children to learn English.
- Qualified teachers should be aware of different types of motivations.
- Learners should be supported with enough study materials.
- Financial incentives or jobs with the English language should be given to students to inspire them.

Conclusion:

Finally, the author admits that many factors influence learners' Motivation differently at different levels. Above all, Motivation plays a crucial role in Learning the English language, and a deep study requires understanding the various factors responsible for Motivation and its different types. This research article helps to understand the topic as a significant part of teaching and learning English as a second or foreign language. The author recommends that such a study enables learners and teachers to achieve the highest possible objectives of learning English with transparent visions of the language.

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